

Rice blast (B1) pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in Tamil Nadu, India

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B1 was a major problem in Tamil Nadu until resistant rice varieties were introduced in the 1960s. Even B1 incidence in susceptible varieties was low until 1980. Since 1980, B1 incidence has increased for all varieties and has become a serious constraint to rice production.

P. oryzae, the causal fungus, was isolated from the infected leaves and inoculated on the international differentials and other varieties to assess their reaction (see table). The isolate of *P. oryzae* did not infect Raminad Str. 3, NP125, Usen, and Dular, which are indicators of the IA, IC, ID, and IE international race groups. Earlier reports had indicated that the *P. oryzae* isolates in Tamil Nadu belong to the race groups IA, IC, ID, and IF, which infect Raminad Str. 3, NP125, Usen, and Kanto 51.

Our observations indicate some changes in the pathogen population, based on the susceptible reaction of Dular and the other varieties which were considered field resistant. □

Reaction of international differentials or varieties to the *P. oryzae* isolate of Tamil Nadu, India. ^a

Differential cultivars and varieties	Indicator	Type of reaction
Raminad	IA	Lesions, B type
Zenith	IB	No reaction
NP125	IC	Lesions, D type
Usen	ID	Lesions, C type
Dular	IE	Lesions, D type
Kanto 51	IF	No reaction
CI 8970	IG	Not tested
Caloro	IH	No reaction
CI 5309		Flecks, A type
Fukunishiki		Lesions, D type
Aichi-Asahi		No reaction
Ishikari Shiroke		Lesions, C type
Chokoto		No reaction
Tsuyuake		No reaction
Taichung (TCWC)		Flecks, A type
Wagwag		Lesions, C type
Sha-tiao-tsao		No reaction
Khao-tah-haeng 17		Flecks, A type
CI 8985 Lacrosse		No reaction
Peta		No reaction
Pai-kan-tao		No reaction
Pi No. 4		No reaction
Yashiromochi		No reaction
Co 25 (xx)		Flecks, A type
Kataktara D42		Lesions, D type
CI 5309		Lesions, D type
IR50		Lesions, D type
Annapoorna		Flecks, A type
Akashi		Lesions, C type
Rasi (x)		No reaction
Co 41		Lesions, B type
Co 39		Lesions, B type
IR36		No reaction
IR28		No reaction

Co 29	No reaction
ADT31	No reaction
Ponmani (x)	Lesions, B type
TKM9	Lesions, D type
Co 43 (x)	No reaction
PY 1	Flecks, A type
MDU 1	Lesions, B type
Bhavani	No reaction
ASD15	Lesions, D type
Co 44	Lesions, C type
ADT36 (x)	Lesions, B type
ADT35 (x)	Lesions, B type
Co 42	Lesions, B type
TKM6	No reaction
Co 36	Lesions, D type
IR20	Flecks, A type
IR22	Lesions, B type
IR34	No reaction
IR54	No reaction
Jaya	Lesions, D type
Paiyur 1	Lesions, B type
Ponni	Lesions, B type
ACK 1	Lesions, D type
ACM 2	Lesions, C type
ACM 3	No reaction
TI 1334	No reaction
AS688	No reaction
AC19789	Lesions, B type
TP1974	No reaction
Py 2	No reaction
Vaigai (x)	Lesions, B type
Pennai	Lesions, D type
Kaveri	Lesions, D type
Co 33	Lesions, B type
Kannagi	Lesions, D type
Kanchi	Lesions, B type

^a A = flecks, B = reddish brown spot, C circular spots (1 mm) with a central white speck, D = spindle lesions (2 mm). (x) = field resistant, (xx) = resistant.

Methods and timing of fungicide application to control rice blast (B1) under favorable upland conditions in Colombia

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Timing of foliar fungicide application to control B1 is based mainly on growth stage or a chronological schedule. However, timing can be flexible if it is based on actual disease development at a given growth stage as influenced by weather, particularly rain in the tropics.

Under favorable upland conditions in Colombia, most of the foliar fungicide applications can be replaced with seed treatment. Furthermore, field observations indicate that additional application

Effects of method and timing of fungicide application on B1 severity and yield of CICA4, Santa Rosa, Villavicencio, Colombia. ^a

Applications (no.)	Treatment ^b		B1 severity (%)		Yield (t/ha)
	For leaf B1	For panicle B1	Leaf	Panicle	
3-4	1. Seed treatment 2. Foliar application for more than 5% infection before maximum tillering	3. Booting stage 4. 50% panicle emergence	9.7 b	3.3 b	4.1 a
4	1. Initial symptom 2. Maximum tillering	3. Booting stage 4. 50% panicle emergence	14.3 b 3.7 c	5.7 b 2 b	4 a 4.2 a
6	1. 30 d after sowing (DAS) 2. 40 DAS 3. 50 DAS 4. 60 DAS	5. 80 DAS 6. 60% panicle emergence			
0	No chemical application		51 a	40.7 a	2.4 b

^a Means of 3 experiments, 3 replications/experiment. In a column, values with common letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Foliar application (300 g ai/ha) and seed treatment (1.1 g ai/kg of seeds) were made with tricyclazole (WP 75%).